

START ON SUSTAINABILITY – INITIAL CONSULTATION ANALYSIS REPORT

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SUMMARY

The consultation on the “Start on Sustainability (SOS) Starter Kit” across micro enterprises in several European countries revealed that the initiative has been highly effective in creating awareness and encouraging businesses to adopt sustainable practices. Enterprises generally define sustainability as minimizing environmental impact, improving efficiency, and ensuring long-term business viability while also contributing to social well-being through education, community engagement, and ethical practices. Sustainability is regarded as essential not only for environmental and societal benefits but also for reputation, innovation, customer trust, and business opportunities.

Enterprises reported contributions to sustainability such as promoting eco-friendly practices, reducing waste, recycling, sourcing locally, supporting women empowerment, creating inclusive workplaces, and offering training to youth and communities. At the same time, they face challenges including financial limitations, lack of cost-efficient tools, urban-rural divides, social inequalities, limited awareness, and sector-specific barriers such as rapid market changes or access to sustainable resources.

Feedback on the SOS Starter Kit was largely positive, with most enterprises either fully or partially agreeing that it covered essential details and aspects. However, suggestions for improvement were consistent across countries. These included adding practical strategies tailored to micro enterprises, highlighting financial and cost-saving benefits of sustainability, providing case studies and industry-specific examples, integrating ESG (environmental, social, and governance) frameworks, and including tools to measure and communicate sustainability impact. Other recommendations emphasized continuous updates, clearer communication, and localized adaptations to reflect sectoral and cultural differences.

Overall, the SOS Starter Kit has proven valuable in promoting sustainability among micro enterprises, but its long-term effectiveness will rely on practical guidance, financial strategies, and tools that help businesses adapt sustainability into everyday operations while ensuring social inclusion and economic resilience.

RESPONSES SUMMARY (TABLE)

S.No	Country	Number of responses
1	Ireland	6
2	Germany	8
3	Spain	6
4	Denmark	4
5	Poland	7

ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES FROM IRELAND

The wide spread of awareness on sustainability among micro enterprises in Ireland was highly successful using “SOS starter kit” – English version. In order to understand the impact of SOS starter kit, the target groups were encouraged to participate in a consultation form named “Consultation on Start on sustainability (SOS) starter kit”. The Consultation form was concise to four private questions and three feedback questions.

1. How do you define sustainability in the context of your business?

In the media and computer industry prioritising eco friendly practices like energy efficient equipment, minimizing waste through digital tools, selecting sustainable suppliers for materials, minimizing printing services, recycling computer parts and promoting second hand equipment. Few enterprises in other sectors believe in educating clients, making more courses on sustainability for the upcoming industry needs and breaking down barriers by working closely with local communities and business.

2. How important is sustainability to your micro-enterprise?

The impact sustainability is witnessed on environmental and societal grounds. It has led to the promotion of business longevity by promoting efficiency, innovation and community engagement. It is important for educators to create courses that meet the relevant needs of work force.

3. In what ways do you believe your micro-enterprise contributes to social sustainability?

One meticulous response on promoting women empowerment, creating wearable that are women friendly, supporting educations and advocating social issues was found. Other responses were mostly based on creating positive social impact, taking ethical decision, sourcing locally leading to cutting down on carbon footprint, offering financial advice for young entrepreneurs and engaging in local voluntary activities. Some enterprise also engages in educating senior members on usage of digital tools and to people with less familiarity on technology. Among designers, the space for creating cultural awareness for people with common thoughts can build relationships. They also include promoting new designers and artist for the livelihood as contribution.

4. Are there social challenges you find particularly important?

One major common social challenge witnessed was the urban rural divide in Ireland, which leads to opportunity being one sided. Mental health issues and the lack of community to address it is also considered as a hurdle. Gender inequality, women contribution getting unrecognised due to stereotypes and digital blockage are other notable mentions too.

5. Does the guidebook cover all the important details?

With success indicators being measured by the response of the target groups, it is overwhelming to see that 90% of the target group have completely agreed and the rest have partially agreed. It is evident that no member has disagreed to the impact of guidebook.

6. Does the outline cover all the aspects that I can think of?

Majority of the enterprises completely agree that the outline covers all the aspect which are necessary.

7. Provide your suggestions for improvement of the guidebook content

Some of the common topics suggested by target groups are: future proofing, introduction to sustainability for micro enterprises, practical environmental sustainability for micro enterprises, social responsibility and community engagement for micro enterprises, financial sustainability strategies, measuring & communicating sustainability impact, case studies & practical examples, continuous improvement and adaptation for micro enterprises.

ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES FROM GERMANY

The wide spread of awareness on sustainability among micro enterprises in Germany was highly successful using “SOS starter kit” – German version. In order to understand the impact of SOS starter kit, the target groups were encouraged to participate in a consultation form named “Consultation on Start on sustainability (SOS) starter kit”. The Consultation form was concise to four private questions and three feedback questions.

1. How do you define sustainability in the context of your business?

German enterprises are more concerned about the future, which is indicated in the statement to make sure the future generations meet the necessary needs. Some of common definitions include, minimizing ecological footprint, fostering responsibility among young minds, good governance and better green mindset at workplace. Enterprises in the supply chain believe to source organic local products and optimum usage of sources. One particular response from trading enterprise recognises to see the future risk and market conditions as definition of sustainability.

2. How important is sustainability to your micro-enterprise?

As micro enterprises are emerging to the market they require the support of customers. With majority of customers expectation relating to sustainability, they believe that sustainability helps them build reputation, meet expectations of social responsibility, increase innovation and bring in more business opportunities. With good understanding about the importance of sustainability enterprises show them in actions by using cars, train and avoiding flight travels.

3. In what ways do you believe your micro-enterprise contributes to social sustainability?

The textile industry contributes by creating awareness on textile waste, educating stakeholders on valuable solutions for textile and sourcing from local artisans and farmers. Local sourcing contributes to livelihood and builds a employment opportunity. Some of the other responses include fair labour practice, positive & inclusive work environment, educating and empowerment of community on choosing better products, prioritising health & well being. In trading industry, providing employee with financial and social benefits, conducting workshops and training make people recognise the market in a better manner.

4. Are there social challenges you find particularly important?

The common challenge among enterprises are lack of social inclusion and economic disparity. Some believe bad access to health care & education, while some think on environmental degradation with disproportion on marginalised community. The textile industry face challenge to keep up with the rapid changing fashion market along with the need to use non harmful chemicals. Some enterprise believes the old business model are become worn out for the rapid market. They would want many enterprises to believe sustainability as a money saving method than just an environmental cause. The trading sector are concerned about the employee quality and declining customer profile.

5. Does the guidebook cover all the important details?

With success indicators being measured by the response of the target groups, it is overwhelming to see that 80% of the target group have completely agreed and the rest have partially agreed. It is evident that no member has disagreed to the impact of guidebook.

6. Does the outline cover all the aspects that I can think of?

From the responses of the enterprises, we can infer that 2/3rd of the enterprises completely agree that the outline covers all the aspect which are necessary with rest partially agreeing to it.

7. Provide your suggestions for improvement of the guidebook content

Some of the suggestions were to include case studies between companies with and without sustainable approach in order to highlight the achievements and working manner. Some topic suggestions are regenerative culture, ESG (environmental, social and governance), local regulation, global modifications and sustainable community.

ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES FROM SPAIN

The wide spread of awareness on sustainability among micro enterprises in SPAIN was highly successful using “SOS starter kit” – Spanish version. In order to understand the impact of SOS starter kit, the target groups were encouraged to participate in a consultation form named “Consultation on Start on sustainability (SOS) starter kit”. The Consultation form was concise to four private questions and three feedback questions.

1. How do you define sustainability in the context of your business?

It was inferred that majority of the enterprise’s view on sustainability was limited to minimizing resources, recycling and minimizing wastes (paper, cardboard) and using minimum energy sources. Some of them viewed it as the next big shift in the industry and are planning their projects with sustainability as one of their criterions.

2. How important is sustainability to your micro-enterprise?

Since sustainability has become a status symbol, many enterprises believe that it could have a positive impact on their business. Due to their customers demand, enterprises consider it as a technological opportunity to lead in the market. Few enterprises are willing to adapt it at the early stage for their long-term business.

3. In what ways do you believe your micro-enterprise contributes to social sustainability?

On analysing the materialistic outcomes, usage of electric vehicles turned out to be major contributing factor for many enterprises. Electrical usage was reduced by solar power and recycling, utilisation of bio-degradable products was witnessed too. Enterprise also use digital documentation to be eco - friendly. Enterprises also consider training young entrepreneurs and helping companies reach energy targets as a major contribution to sustainability.

4. Are there social challenges you find particularly important?

“Lack of finance” has been identified as common challenge faced by all micro enterprises. The lack of cost-efficient tools and personalised solutions are major concerns. It was noticed that regulations with better incentives for research or incentives with alternatives would also be encouraged. Lack of awareness to consider investment on sustainability as a path to growth needed to be encouraged. The need for a common sustainable model for easy adaptation was also requested.

5. Does the guidebook cover all the important details?

50% of the target group completely agrees to it while rest are believed to have fairly agreed to it.

6. Does the outline cover all the aspects that I can think of?

Based on the responses majority have fairly agreed to it making a positive success of the SOS starter kit.

7. Provide your suggestions for improvement of the guidebook content

Enterprises proposed to add information directing to financial and cost benefits of sustainability. It was also recommended to add ISO standard for energy usage. More information about available tools and energy saving procedures would be encouraged.

ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES FROM DENMARK

The wide spread of awareness on sustainability among micro enterprises in Denmark was highly successful using “SOS starter kit” – Danish version. In order to understand the impact of SOS starter kit, the target groups were encouraged to participate in a consultation form named “Consultation on Start on sustainability (SOS) starter kit”. The Consultation form was concise to four private questions and three feedback questions.

1. How do you define sustainability in the context of your business?

Many consumer-based business believe encouragement of local products promotes sustainability by minimising transport and maximising recycling. The most common understanding is believed to be the usage of energy efficient devices like light bulbs and digital tools. The food industry defines by using innovative menu design to minimise food wastage wherein the computer industry is more focussed on minimising carbon footprints.

2. How important is sustainability to your micro-enterprise?

Every member of the target group, commonly believe that the necessity to opt for sustainability is due to the demand from their customer base. All though sustainability is beneficial for the planet, business longevity and customer loyalty with same values are seen to take an upper hand.

3. In what ways do you believe your micro-enterprise contributes to social sustainability?

The most common dissemination strategy is found to be support of local community by using local products and promoting local exclusivity. Since people play an important role in success of micro enterprises than money, majority believe in creating a welcomed environment for the customers and creating a positive workplace for the employees. Members from the computer industry believe to contribute by designing digital tools accessible to whole of the diverse community.

4. Are there social challenges you find particularly important?

Members of the food industry find the equal access to healthy & sustainable food with affordability as a major social challenge. Also addressing the diverse needs of the community by smaller and personalised steps are also found to be a hurdle.

5. Does the guidebook cover all the important details?

With success indicators being measured by the response of the target groups, it is overwhelming to see that one half of the target group have completely agreed and the other half have partially agreed. It is evident that no member has disagreed to the impact of guidebook.

6. Does the outline cover all the aspects that I can think of?

Majority of the enterprises partially agree that the outline covers all the aspect which are necessary.

7. Provide your suggestions for improvement of the guidebook content

One of the most common suggestion ins the addition of diverse case studies and industry specific advice & strategies. The second most common requirement is to enlighten more on digital tools which help in knowledge about sustainability in operations and supply chain. The final suggestion was to include means to measure the impact of sustainability on respective businesses and promote cost benefits of sustainability.

ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES FROM POLAND

The wide spread of awareness on sustainability among micro enterprises in Poland was highly successful using “SOS starter kit” – Polish version. In order to understand the impact of SOS starter kit, the target groups were encouraged to participate in a consultation form named “Consultation on Start on sustainability (SOS) starter kit”. The Consultation form was concise to four private questions and three feedback questions.

1. How do you define sustainability in the context of your business?

The Poland target group had a matured way to define sustainability. Some of the definitions are stability in planning and implementation of tasks, limited usage of printing materials and avoiding plastics. The most common response was to achieve growth without having negative impacts on the environment.

2. How important is sustainability to your micro-enterprise?

For some enterprises, “Sustainability” is the foundation of their business. Therefore, they depict the importance though limiting usage of negative impactful packing waste, used equipment, used batteries and accumulators. Some of the ethical responses are directed towards applying codes of ethics, encouraging space for activities and more focus on ESG areas.

3. In what ways do you believe your micro-enterprise contributes to social sustainability?

Staffs and people are the pillars of micro enterprises, therefore training and education are the core believes of major enterprises. Some enterprises believe in ethical practices like conscious decision and planning, providing salary on time with safe functioning in society and least energy consumption.

4. Are there social challenges you find particularly important?

The enterprises fear that the advancement of artificial intelligence could be a hurdle in people employment whereas on the other side with ageing population, human services are expected to be premium standards. Some of the common hurdles are social inequality and lack of inclusion and lack of cooperation between institution and government. A specific lack of knowledge on the subsidies from EU is one of the highlighted challenges along with people competence in the current market.

5. Does the guidebook cover all the important details?

With success indicators being measured by the response of the target groups, it is satisfying to see that majority of the target group have partially agreed and the rest have a diversified opinion with few completely agreeing.

6. Does the outline cover all the aspects that I can think of?

The synchronisation in the responses of both the questions are the perfect with majority of the target group partially agreeing and a few completely agreeing.

7. Provide your suggestions for improvement of the guidebook content

The basic suggestion provided was the need to use an alternative word for “sustainability” in order to avoid translation confusion. Tips like, to have a social psychologist view on the project, increasing NGO participation, sharing experiences of sustainable companies and educating staff members on sustainability awareness was witnessed. Some of the topics suggested by enterprises are New regulatory requirements, ESG risk management, value chain, sustainable development strategy and responsible business practices and methods to obtain financing for green investment.